

Cultural Practices and Primary School Completion of the Girl-Child in Gokana Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the impacts of cultural practices on the girl-child completion of primary school in Gokana Local Government Area (LGA) of Rivers State (R/S), Nigeria. While descriptive research design stood espoused, three each of research questions as well as null hypotheses steered the study. The latter espoused 1,879 female pupils in lower basic as its population. The sample for the study was 185 female pupils. The researcher designed questionnaire espoused for assemblage of facts. All collated facts stood analyzed via the non-dependent t-test. Result of the outcomes showed substantial impacts of parental male favour on girl-child completion of primary school; there is a significant influence of traditional gender-roles on girl-child completion of primary school; there also exist substantial impact of large family size on girl-child completion of primary school.

Key words: Cultural practices, Girl-child, male-preference, gender-roles, completion

Introduction

Girl child academic-training is a substantial contributory element to monetary expansion as well as a key to supportable development. In this age of globalization, the education of the girl-child is seen as a tactical asset in humanoid as well as intellectual investment. Nevertheless, the background realities for girl-broods in addition to the status of their schooling in Africa are depressing. In sub-Saharan Africa, illiteracy amid womenfolk continues to be heighten owing to the incapability of the republics to enroll as well as sustain girl-progenies in schools (UNESCO, 1993).

Education is a tool for procurement facts, expertise in addition to assertiveness for work, home as well as personhood. For womenfolk, a worthy education brands them enhanced mums as well as home-formers, creative personnel in addition to accountable populaces. Anderson, (1988) asserts that academic-training enriches womenfolk's capability to exhibit their privileges as well as duties. The right to possess land, for instance, is lessened by the incapability to recite as well as comprehend agreements or to perform simple calculation. The right to ballot is worthless if womenfolk could notify themselves of the concerns of this time. Anderson contends likewise that ferocity counter to womenfolk in the family or on the thoroughfares has remained linked not just with insufficiency but similarly with illiteracy, which thwarts womenfolk from declaring their rights as well as defending themselves by seeking due procedure of law. Summers (1993) records that the academic-training of females affords confidence for contravention of the series of females' denial as well as lack.

Dropping out of progenies from school has remained a challenging issue in countless places everywhere in the world (Young & Chavez, 2002), specifically in low revenue nations. Lewin and Sabates, (2012) opined that even though huge amount of progenies currently start basic school compared to ever before, the degree at which progenies drop out from school has stood high in subordinate republics. More than half of the progenies who start basic school do not complete the full sequence of schooling, with traditional barricades, amid others, being a causal factor.

Socio-cultural blockades i.e. communal standards, regulations as well as rubrics, principles in addition to practices hinder females' involvement in academic-training (Tanye, 2008). The old-style setting is ethnically entrenched and as such deters lassies' from liking their humanoid individuality as well as social rights. Correspondingly, the ethnic approach with regards to womenfolk's schooling (the dowry system, control of womenfolk's lives, male privilege, time restraints, womenfolk's absence of self-confidence, and a lot of roles that females' play) avert their schooling (Tanye, 2008; Lambert, Perrino, & Barreras, 2012).

Countless parentages opine that funding the academic-training of the girl-child is useless of funds therefore the sooner the girl go into nuptial the healthier. Chernichovsky (1985) clarified that the choice of exact child for academic-training requires not be sex prejudiced. In the face of sim funds, the masculine youngster remains habitually favored, as well, this signifies an approach to diffuse danger. Several resolve to train only progenies who they presume will do well in school as well as succeed in receiving a well-paid occupation, which could aid the household. It follows that, the masculine kid is favored. It could, consequently, be explicated that the male teenager is desired to go to school at the expense of the girl child. Teenager favour favour the male child.

The male-progenies are expected to be able to do phenomenally in the world of knowledge and technology, while a woman's place is at home, keeping up with the livelihood of the family (World Bank 2003). Entirely household growth struggles, comprising academic-pursuit remain devoted on the boys since they are trustd to be the creators of tribes, whereas the lassies are anticipated to be married off to spouses who expresses their behalf. Accordingly, minimal energies as well as funds are committed on lassies' improvement in over-all.

Countless parentages embrace the opinion that the traditional roles of girl-progenies remains to tie the knot, propagate, upkeep for the household as well as continue to care for the kitchenette, in addition to household workers, hence devoting funds into their academic-training is useless of funds (Lambert, Perrino, & Barreras, 2012; Plan, 2012). Consequently, to play these roles efficiently could not demand womenfolk to have advanced academic-training certifications thereby repudiating them the right to academic-training (Tanye, 2008).

In corroborating this view, Lambert *et al.*, (2012) led a study in non-urban central region of Ghana on the issues working contrary to lassies' registering in schools and completing school, particularly throughout their movement from Junior-high school to senior-high school and discovered that the insight of parentages in the study area was that it remains more sensible to propel their mannish child to school. Even if the feminine youngster goes to school, she will get married, have kids, as well as work in the kitchenette.

Specific parentages opine that higher academic-training impacts the ethical lives of womenfolk; they have the awareness that extremely educated womenfolk are actual problematic to marry since they cannot turn into worthy spouses, or distinguish how to cook (Tanye, 2008). To Tanye, this sort of approach from parentages, household associates, as well as women themselves contribute to their marginalization and the completion of their academic-training.

Reports from Admassie (2003) and Boyle, Brock, Mace, & Sibbons (2002) show the favour countless family-circle have for the academic-training of boys over lassies. In certain philosophies, lassies are made to partake on home tasks, in addition boys frequently acquire favour once parentages have to select who in sex-footings goes school. Notwithstanding, in countless African philosophies, division of work is by sex as well as age, in addition to femaleness is related with inactiveness and necessity whereby lassies are elevated to trust that they must not seek for high statures since their work is principally about the kitchenette.

Similarly, GESS (2013) states that customarily, together the family as well as communal consider, lassies singly as upcoming wives, as well as mothers. Lassies are elevated as well as socialized to also view themselves in this light. Nevertheless, a report in Kenya by Amadi, Role, and Makewa (2013) posited that substantial dissimilarities exist in the insights of tutors and scholars on ethnic standards, healthiness as well as gravidity, as elements impacting to dropout amid supplementary issues.

Traditional-gender-roles of lassies in the households avert them from joining school or outstanding in school. Lassies unlike boys remain anticipated to aid their mothers with household tasks. This goes a long way to hinder their development in academic-training or lead to outright dropout of school as they have no time to study. Consequently, it is astute to opine that progenies who drop out are more or less betrothed in household tasks in addition to diverse sorts of labor outside their home in mandate to retain themselves in addition to their families in their daily events. Predominantly, lassies from non-urban areas engage themselves in cooking food, cleaning paraphernalia, gathering firewood, caring of the youngsters outside agricultural periods. Throughout agricultural period, lassies are betrothed in farming events beside family circle.

Alhassan (2005) argued that lassies unlike boys are estimated to aid their mommies with household tasks. This, further retards their improvement in academic-training as there will be no time for studies. Home tasks which are generalised gender roles to feminine in basic societies, controls their involvement in school. Household tasks conferred on lassies in certain homes leave them with be basically no time for schoolwork, which presupposes that countless lassies come to classes in an exhausted state. These household overload lassies face initial in life, may hamper their chances for imaginative reasoning, learning and school completion (Buraka, 2006, Fant, 2008).

In corroborating this view, Manandhar and Sthapit (2011) in carrying a study on reasons of dropout of girl-progenies in primary schools in Nawalparasi district of Nepal, established that practically 50% girl-progenies dropout owing to their duties in household tasks. Majority of these progenies look after their young relatives when their parentages go for work. Virtually every child who dropped out from school, precisely in the non-urban as well as inaccessible areas in addition from not to do-well families, is betrothed in certain form of toil or task. Though, girl-progenies combine work with school in the start and certain are registered later, they are incapable to complete their full cycle of educating (Colclough Rose, & Tembon, 2000).

Large family size plays an imperative part when it comes to enrolling the progenies to school. The lassie teenager is continuously at detriment when it comes to who must go to school and as of the several glitches that definite large families encounter. They give out certain of their progenies specifically the feminine progenies out as maid helps in the non-rural areas. Nevertheless, in these areas, the girl-progenies are permitted not to go to school, as well as even certain times not accorded appropriate upkeep.

Alhassan (2005) opined that large family plays an imperative role when it comes to enrolling the progenies to school. Alhassan maintained that parentages are incapable to meet the cost of their progenies' academic-training owing to the heavy tasks of caring for all the progenies and the wives in the family.

The government, in recent times have encouraged gender equality to advance the right of entry of female progenies to primary education as to permit their complete involvement and completion in academic-training. The study examined the influence of cultural practices on primary school completion of the girl-child in Gokana LGA of R/S.

Statement of the problem

Primary education is imperative for socio-economic expansion in any societies. This is owing to the fact that, primary academic-training is rudimentary, as it is a base for junior as well as progressive secondary phase in addition to tertiary stage, so partaking of females to the greater stages of academic-training is resolute by partaking rate at primary level. The cumulating of poor partaking rate in academic-training hamper the delivery of education and it is pre-dominant to primary school female pupils. This impacts the primary school female accomplishment rates as well as their possible progression of talents.

Also, poor partaking of female pupils in academic-training influences asset initiatives on female which has more socio-economic values, as the World Bank (2013), states that, educating a girl is one of the sturdiest ways to encourage financial progress as well as healthiness expansion of kinfolks, societies as well as countries. Through this view there is a need to highlight on female partaking in academic-training so as to evade disparity in accessing and advancement of education.

The practice where parentages prefer their male progenies for schooling if there is the need to choose which of their progenies goes to school is a common practice in the study area, also, the cultural practice where the girl-child is trained to take care of the home in meal preparation, cleaning of the house, helping the mother in selling her wares, all inhibit the girl-child's completion of primary school in the study area.

The government, in recent times have encouraged gender equality to enhance the access of female progenies to primary education in order to allow their full partaking and completion in academic-training. The study examined the influence of cultural practices on primary school completion of the girl-child in Gokana LGA of R/S.

Research Question

The subsequent research questions remained answered for this study:

1. Does parental male preference influence the girl-child completion of primary school in Gokana LGA?
2. Does traditional-gender-roles influence the girl-child completion of primary school in Gokana LGA?
3. To what degree does large family size influence the girl-child completion of primary in Gokana LGA?

Research hypotheses

The corresponding null hypotheses stood tested

1. No substantial influence of parental male preference on the girl-child completion of primary school exist in Gokana LGA.
2. Traditional-gender-roles does not significantly influence the girl-child completion of primary school in Gokana LGA.
3. No significant influence of large family size on the girl-child completion of primary school exist in Gokana LGA.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed descriptive survey research design, which is the methodical assemblage of facts in consistent manner from a recognisable populace. This design is suitable for this study since the researcher will not manipulate the data but will use them as they are in their state. The population of the study consisted of 1,879 female pupils in the Lower basic in the 42 public primary schools in Gokana LGA (R/S Universal Basic Education Board, 2019). 185 female pupils in the lower basic which represents 10.1% of the total populace remained sampled for the study. The simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the sample size from five public primary schools. The instrument for data assemblage remained the researcher designed questionnaire titled “Cultural Practices and Primary School Completion of the Girl-Child Questionnaire (CPPSCGQ)”. The questionnaire had two sections: A and B. Section A had items covering the demography of the respondents. Section B had 20 items that was used in testing the null hypotheses. The questionnaire had four scales which were scored in the following manner: Strongly Agree (SA)=4, Agree (A)=3, Disagree (D)=2, and Strongly Disagree (SD)=1. The instrument was validated by three experts in the department of Early Childhood and Primary Education, Ignatius Ajuru University. Their inputs were used in modifying the final draft of the instrument for content and face validity. The instrument was administered to female pupils in public primary schools in Khana LGA, who were not part of the study. The data collected was analysed using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient to determine the reliapability index. The reliapability coefficient of the instrument was found to be 0.732 which made the instrument reliable for this study. In administering the instrument, research permit was first obtained from the head-teachers of the sampled schools. Afterwards the researcher with the help of the research helpers proceeded to administer the instrument to the respondents. Explanations was given in areas that the respondents may not understand. The researcher collected the completed instruments at the end of the session in each study centre at the spot after two hours. The data collected was analyzed using the independent t-test in testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and discussion of findings

Research hypothesis one: There is no significant influence of parental male preference on the girl-child completion of primary school in Gokana Local Government Area.

Table 1: Summary of independent t-test for parental male preference and girl-child completion of primary school

Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t _{cal}	t _{crit}	Decision
Male preference	91	3.18	0.713				
Female preference	94	3.02	0.802				
Total	185	6.20	1.515	183	2.481	1.96	Reject Ho

Table 1 gives the summary of the t-test analysis for influence of parental male preference on the girl-child completion of primary school. The calculated t-value is 2.481. At 183 degree of freedom and .05 level of significance, the critical t-value from table is 1.96. Since the t_{cal} is greater than the t_{crit}, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a substantial influence of parental male preference on girl-child completion of primary school pupil.

This finding supports the views of Lambert, Perrino, & Barreras (2012) who states that countless parentages hold the understanding that the traditional roles of girl-progenies are to marry, breed, upkeep for the household and continue in the kitchenette, and as home labourers, consequently devoting funds into their academic-training is a waste of resources. The result also supports the findings of Boyle, Brock, Mace, and Sibbons (2002) who established that lassies are left to take on household responsibilities, and boys frequently acquire favour when parentages have to choose who in gender terms attends school.

Research hypothesis two: Traditional-gender-roles does not significantly influence the girl-child completion of primary school in Gokana Local Government Area.

Table 2: Summary of t-test for traditional gender-roles and girl-child completion of primary school

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t _{cal}	t _{crit}	Decision
Traditional gender-roles for female	98	3.24	0.77				
Traditional gender-roles for male	87	2.94	0.72				
Total	185	6.18	1.49	183	2.738	1.96	Reject Ho

Table 2 gives the summary of the t-test analysis for influence of traditional gender-roles on girl-child completion of primary school. The calculated t-value is 2.738. At 183 degree of freedom and .05 level of significance, the critical t-value from table is 1.96. Since the t_{cal} is greater than the t_{crit}, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a substantial influence of traditional gender-roles on girl-child completion of primary school.

This finding is in agreement with the views of Alhassan (2005) who advocates that whether lassies are in schools or not they have to cook, wash, clean, and fetch water in the household. This goes a long way to retard their progress in academic-training as they have no time to study and are always tired after such work. Also, the finding supports the findings of Manandhar and Sthapit (2011) who in their study found that almost half of the girl-progenies dropout is owing to their responsibilities in household tasks.

Research hypothesis three: There is no significant influence of large family size on the girl-child completion of primary school in Gokana Local Government Area.

Table 3: Summary of analysis of independent t for large family size and girl-child completion of primary school

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t _{cal}	t _{crit}	Decision
Large family size	97	3.14	0.73				
Small family size	88	3.05	0.79				
Total	185	6.19	1.52	183	2.77	1.96	Reject Ho

Table 3 gives the summary of the t-test analysis for influence of large family size on girl-child completion of primary school. The calculated t-value is 2.77. At 183 degree of freedom and .05 level of significance, the critical t-value from table is 1.96. Since the t_{cal} is greater than the t_{crit}, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a substantial influence of large family size on girl-child completion of primary school.

The finding is in support of the views of Alhassan (2005) who opined that large family plays an imperative role it concerns directing progenies to school. Alhassan maintained that parentages are incapable to meet the cost of their progenies academic-training owing to the weighty tasks of caring every wife.

Conclusion

The education of the girl-child is very imperative in the progression as well as expansion of humanity. The academic-training of the girl-child is impeded by cultural practices which debar the girl-child from completing her primary education. The parental male favour, traditional gender-roles, large family size and early marriage substantially influences the girl-child completion of primary school, which invariably effect their overall academic-training in life.

Recommendations

The resulting recommendations stood framed based on the outcomes of the study:

1. Parentages should learn to give every child equal opportunity in educational training, irrespective of the gender of the child, so as to develop the full potential of the girl-child.
2. The government and community leaders should ensure that obnoxious traditional practices that cage the girl-child are discarded so that the girl-child can contribute meaningfully in the society.
3. The non-government, through the ministry of social welfare, should enlighten the parentages on the need for family planning so as to curb the large family syndrome which impacts the academic-training of the girl-child.

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